

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-4, AUGUST 2025

Editor-In-Chief: **Dr. Vishwanath Bite**
Managing Editor: **Dr. Madhuri Bite**

www.the-criterion.com

AboutUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/about/>

Archive: <http://www.the-criterion.com/archive/>

ContactUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/contact/>

EditorialBoard: <http://www.the-criterion.com/editorial-board/>

Submission: <http://www.the-criterion.com/submission/>

FAQ: <http://www.the-criterion.com/fa/>

ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Jessie Greengrass's Novel *The High House*: A Saga of Resilience in the Face of Climate Catastrophe

Dr Sanjogita Tiwari
Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
Rajeev Gandhi Government College, Simga (C.G.)

Article History: Submitted-24/06/2025, Revised-08/08/2025, Accepted-09/08/2025, Published-31/08/2025.

Abstract:

The High House, a 2021 novel by the well-acclaimed British author Jessie Greengrass, is an engrossing work of fiction in the category of climate catastrophe. It is a novel with significant lessons for humanity through its depiction of a post-apocalyptic climate change in its narrative of a close-knit family with two departed parents, two surviving kids along with two caretakers. The protagonist of the novel named Francesca, is a renowned climate change activist with a penchant for accurate predictions about climate change. Unfortunately, she along with her husband falls a victim to a raging storm but before her death she ensures that her children seek refuge in a bluff side home, a High House, in an isolated setting by the seaside. The inhabitants of this house find themselves struggling against an inevitable environmental crisis which no matter how much they try to look askance from, is a glaring truth ready to envelope them in a doom. The present research article highlights the fact that global environmental crisis is nearer than we imagine and it provides important lessons for humanity that we need to pay heed to in order to survive. The paper examines resilience shown in the face of climate catastrophe by the characters of the novel.

Keywords: Apocalypse, Ecosystem, Crisis, Community, Environmental Catastrophe, Predictions, Resilience.

1. Introduction

According to Merriam Webster dictionary, the term 'catastrophe' means a sudden disaster or complete failure. When applied to climatic conditions, climate catastrophe implies a large-scale devastation of life and property accompanied by a considerable upheaval in the physiognomy of the earth. Climate catastrophe may occur in slow and steady steps or in a sudden manner, taking everyone in a surprise. There are many types of reactions by human beings to climate catastrophe, depending on to what extent the life of a human being is impacted. Plants, animals and human beings find it a tough battle for survival to face a climate catastrophe. The environment constantly emits signals of precarious situations ahead. However, if these warning signs are not interpreted properly often it becomes too late to proceed with ameliorative action. The environment constantly emits signals of precarious situations ahead. However, if these warning signs are not interpreted properly, often it becomes too late to proceed with ameliorative action.

The lead character of the novel *The High House* is an environmental scientist. She takes cognizance of the fact that her immediate environment is likely to show catastrophe. She starts preparing the high house as a sanctuary, in the event of an environmental apocalypse. She meets untimely death along with her husband but before that she manages to arrange for a safe abode in a High House in her native village. The present paper highlights how the surviving characters, (the two children and their two caretakers) show resilience and forbearance in the face of apocalyptic situations.

Climate change is not a new phenomenon. Every now and then, climate change brings forth upheavals, much more than anticipated. The magnitude of the disaster often surprises us. In the research article 'Climate Change and Catastrophe' by Ostenova N.K, in the journal *Earth and Environmental Science Research and Reviews* the climatic catastrophe has been described:

Climate change is becoming increasingly catastrophic, and its increasing intensity threatens the death of humanity and the planet as a whole. Anthropogenic pollution of the ocean increases the negativity of the ongoing processes since it can no longer cope with cooling function and emits carbon dioxide instead of oxygen. Knowledge of the properties of natural disaster is intended to contribute to a more objective approach to assessing ongoing events. A catastrophe is the sudden change in the behaviour of a system, and relying on climate adaptation is nothing more than a fallacy, since we are not talking about gradual long-term changes. Suffice it to recall some events: earthquakes in Turkey, Syria or Morocco; floods in China, Italy or Libya; fires in Hawaii, a hurricane in Acapulco. How can you adapt to something that falls under the definition of “suddenly”, how quickly the consequences of these events were eliminated and were they eliminated at all? Predictions can only be made in line with the directions of development, that is, processes strengthen or weaken over time (8).

2. Nature’s Signals or Warnings

Grievous consequences of adverse environmental change was not a hidden fact from Francesca who was a scientist. She observes: “This was when it was still the beginning of things.... stained with mud.” (11-12).

“And all the while, outside, the thing that only she could look at straight : the early springs and two long summers, the sudden unpredictable winters that came from nowhere and brought floods or ice or wind or didn't come, so that there was only day after day of sticky dampness and the leaves rotting on the trees and the birds still singing in December, resting until the snow came at last, and having overlooked migration, they froze on the branches, and they died (*The High House* 20).

Francesca the mother of a six-month-old boy, was worried about their future. All the while she was engaged in decoding the signs of climate catastrophe. Her speech goes: “we must recognise that we are being given a final warning - because if we fail to do so, if we fail to act, the consequences will surpass anything we have previously seen and we will have missed our chance” (21). Only the other day Francesca and her family had watched a live recording of a storm over taking an island in the mid-Pacific. In front of their eyes, they saw the island sink in the sea.

“We saw the storm arrive, the cameras picking up the rain, the swelling wind. We saw doors torn from hinges; palm trees bend and give. We watched as an ordinary piazza in a far - off seaside town came apart, its street signs snapped, lamp posts buckled, the cafe on the corner split open like an egg.” (*The High House* 22).

These happenings watched by the surviving members of the family prepared a foreground for resilience when the climate apocalypse like situation actually set in. Once the storm retreated, the aftermath scene was a sorry state of affairs.

“Next morning, after the storm had moved away, we turned on the television again and saw satellite pictures of the place where the island had been, and where there was nothing now but bare earth and a patch of ocean scummy with debris. The people who had lived there were now in temporary shelters, we were told, on the nearest major landmass, a thousand miles away from where, a week earlier, they had been at home.” (*The High House* 23).

Francesca understood very well that it was already too late to prevent an apocalypse. As she addresses a group of university students in their mourning dresses, “If we are in mourning for anything, it is for a time when we could turn our backs” (27). Her daughter

Caroline is a conscientious girl, observant about her mother's concern for the environment.

Watching news of various kinds on the television, she came across the following news:

“In Bangladesh, the rains had failed. In Japan, there were floods. A delegation from the drowned island had arrived at the UN, seeking restitution. Fires raged through the centre of Australia, and in parts of China, the summer was now so hot and humid that it was incompatible with life.” (*The High House* 32).

Climate was becoming more and more vulnerable to catastrophe with each passing day.

Caroline says,

“It was becoming clear to everyone now that things were getting worse. The winter before, half of Gloucestershire had been flooded, and the waters, refusing to recede, had made a new fen, covering homes and fields, roads, schools, hills rising from it like islands. In York, the river had burst its banks and the city centre was gone, walls which had stood for nearly two millennia halfway down to the Hull.” (*The High House* 38).

Students and other staff of universities and colleges raised awareness campaigns regarding environmental degradation. Sally the caretaker in the High House, could see that such steps were inadequate in view of the gigantic scale of environmental change.

“I was ashamed to feel so parochial, and ashamed as well to notice, among the chants and the handmade banners painted with vegetable dyes, that although the action itself might have brought a temporary relief from anxiety to those who were a part of it, nothing else changed. The plastics were still manufactured, the chemical fertilizers were still used.” (*The High House* 91).

Once the climate catastrophe sets in, resilience by human beings is in high demand. As the characters of the novel witness adversity, they exhibit exemplary grit and determination.

3. A Scientist's Preparations for Climate Change

As a climate scientist, Francesca knew that floods would arrive. This knowledge prompted her to make preparations for the inevitable calamity. She made frequent visits to the High House and began stocking it with all the necessary amenities for survival in case of a climate catastrophe. During one of her visits, she addresses old Grandy, the caretaker of the High House in the following words:

“We can be sure”, she continued, “that floods will come. There’s no doubt on that score. All we can do is protect what might be saved. It’s no good waiting for the government to intervene, because they won’t not pre-emptively. I’ve seen the damage flooding does. The force of the water is unimaginable. It takes everything it can get (*The High House* 95).

Francesca had been interviewing old Grandy about his past experience of having seen his entire village wiped out in floods. Going back in memory lane, Grandy recalled the aftermath of floods whereby every valuable thing was lost. Francesca took note of his experience and began preparing earnestly for each and every repercussion of climate catastrophe. Although she had no idea how long her fortification to keep her children safe would last, she was relentless in her pursuit. However, she along with her husband succumbed to sudden floods; not even their bodies were retrieved.

Michael Richardson, in his article ‘Climate Trauma, or the Affects of the Catastrophe’, in the journal *Environmental Humanities*, expostulates:

“Already arriving from the future yet only just beginning to unfold, climate catastrophe bears down on and shapes the present. It cannot but be felt in the now: in its micro and macro manifestations, in the threat it poses to existing ways of life, in its up-ending of entrenched understanding of the working of the world, and in the injury it does to

particular lives and wider ecologies. Climate catastrophe works on ecologies and bodies alike as a kind of wounding, one not simply or solely to the everyday stuff of biological life but to the very constitution of experience and expressions (1).

4. Catastrophic Days

Nature has a certain abrupt way of defying all human calculations, more so during a climate catastrophe. R.T. Pierrhumbert rightly propounds this fact in the *Chicago Journal of International Law*, in the article under the title ‘Climate Change: A Catastrophe in Slow Motion’.

“In addition, historical evidence shows that the climate system has abrupt switches built into it, and that climate changes in fits and starts rather than along a smooth, gentle curve. Notwithstanding the movie ‘The Day After Tomorrow’, this does not mean that global warming risks bringing on an ice age. Rather, what we risk is a switch to a climate that has much more dramatic swings in it from one decade to the next, making adaptation much more difficult.” (*The High House* 579).

The floods ushered in irreparable loss. All that was soothing in nature, all that used to provide solace for living was suddenly lost. Caroline, the elder daughter of Francesca found herself disappointed for the loss of her parents. She broods over the loss:

“It was extraordinary how quickly things fell apart, in the end. That city, which a day earlier, had been impregnable, glinting bright with glass and power, was swallowed by the sea. The land it had been built on would not be given back. Father and Francesca would not be given back. All the things were forfeit, and along with them, the sense we’d always had that, whatever happened, we would be all right” (*The High House* 53).

Sally, the housekeeper girl loved to watch the swallows. She waited from May to June, to July but the sky was empty of swallows. She guessed that perhaps the swallows had not yet

migrated back, but the entire year passed by and the birds were not seen. She waited and kept waiting for the birds.

“But there was no sign of swallows that year, or the next, and I am still waiting, now. I watch for them each spring, from the kitchen window in the high house. I stand there in the early evening, when the insects rise, still not so numerous, into the dimming air, and I wish for them, for their bullet bodies and the way they have of flickering in flight, their speech and grace- but the sky is still empty. Perhaps there are no swallows left (*The High House* 79).

While Pauly, Sally, Caro and Grandy are sheltered in the High House after the surge of water having deluded their homes as well as Pauly and Caro's parents, they take stock of the situation. Sally says:

“And the internet is patchy. Half the country is under water, as far as I can tell. The Thames has burst its banks above the barrier and God knows how many drowned. They say it's worse in the Netherlands, Belgium and Germany too. Switzerland has closed its borders. The French government say that they have suffered their own damages and don't have the resources to send aid. People have nowhere to go. Some of them were sitting on roofs, making videos of the water rising. Some of them were waiting to die (*The High House* 83).

Sally was a brave heart but she too had grown desolate. She, however, tried to maintain her composure. “But I didn't know how to say what I was thinking. All morning, between the rising spirits brought on by our own escape and the sudden blue skies, and end to rain after weeks of storms, a sense of desolation had come over me in waves (83). Gravely conscious of the damage done to the human as well as animal living space by the floods, Sally reflects:

That night, sitting in bed in the dark with my laptop open on my knees, I looked at photographs of forests and the holes that had been torn in them, the gaping; sore – edged wounds where trees had been, the long, brown scars which were all that was left of the rivers. I tried to see these things as I thought Francesca did: not as a part of that long, slow slide, entropy, which grinds and grinds, which is beyond our interventions, is out of reach , winding us towards our end, but as something fresh and acute – a set of circumstances which could have been prevented, once, but now had gone beyond repair – but it was too much to bear. (*The High House* 127).

The storm which had done away with Francesca and her husband’s life, was still a shock to the community. They had hardly imagined about its enormity. Sally observes:

“The commentary was flat with shock. This was something new, it seemed, this incursion of water into homes. It was the beginning of some second phase: a turning point- except, of course, that it was really only more of the same. We had been watching people drown for years, and the only difference was that they had always been a long way off from us, before. We sent money, perhaps if the pictures were bad enough, and then we went on as we always had.”

“Their deaths, although we didn’t like to say so, were not really a disaster to us, because disaster would only come when it had our own face on it – and now, here it was.” (*The High House* 150).

While still dwelling in the High House after the days of high turbulence, Sally takes note of the changes in the environment and the surroundings.

“With end of Summer, a change came .It had been easy, all through the long holiday weeks, to believe that the high house was a kind of paradise, with everything we could even want stored for us in the barn and nothing to do except keep the garden, or wander

to the beach and back but now the evenings began to darken, the sky inking up while we were still putting Pauly to bed, and still there was no rain. The hedges were dusty. Grass died. (*The High House* 205)

Caroline too like Sally, could feel the vagaries of nature. The uncertainty of weather, brought several inconveniences for them.

“The rain was a constancy but there were variations in it. Sometimes it was a fine mist, a falling mist that lay in drops on hair and clothes like tiny jewels, and at others, it was a steady pouring which found its way inside zips and seams. There were days when the wind blew it into daggers that stung our hands, our faces. There were days when it was nothing more than a never - ending background of wet and grey, and even once, an afternoon when I stood on the embankment by the river and watched the clouds part, out at sea, to let a shaft of sunlight through which split and glittered and made a rainbow over the heath. Mostly it was only rain. (*The High House* 219).

Sally recognizes the precarious nature of the situation they were facing. The aftermath of the apocalyptic condition was equally challenging. She mentions:

Besides the threat of water, there was the threat of hunger. Farm animals floated, drowned, in flooded fields. The earth was too wet to yield a crop. Ports, inundated, evacuated, struggled to give harbour to those few container ships which still come. The whole complicated system of modernity which had held us up, away from the earth, was crumbling, and we were becoming again what we had used to be: cold, and frightened of the weather, and frightened of the dark (*The High House* 226).

The village adjacent to the High House was completely submerged in water. Caroline and Sally went to ring the church bell, to warn of the flood to any probable survivors or

remnants. They rang the bell overnight, till their palms blistered. They would not stop till Grandy and Pauly came to call them back to safety in the High House. As Sally recounts,

“All night we tolled the church bell. We pulled the rope until our hands blistered, and the blisters split up and then bled, until the skin of our palms was raw, and then we pulled again, and the sound of it was a slow beat out across the night. We pulled it until dawn broke, and the sun rose, and then at last we stopped (*The High House* 261).

Thus, Sally saw her own village sink and felt helpless about it. Grandy had seen this kind of a happening while he was still a child. For Sally it was an event full of pathos, helplessness and frustration.

Sally was worried about other people on this planet. Though she was safe along with her people, she understood that a large number of people elsewhere were a part of the suffering humanity. She writes:

In the evenings, in darkness, after the others were in bed, I sat at the bottom of the stairs, my fists balled against my eyelids, exhausted, overwrought, but too afraid to call a halt to the day because I knew that, lying in bed, waiting for sleep, would be when the desolation came, and the thought of all the people – all those who, elsewhere, were dying, from hunger or drought, fire or wind or frost, while I, in my sanctuary, scrubbed out my anger against the floorboards with soap and water (*The High House* 207).

Sally mentions that December came and it had been raining, for six weeks. The roads had flooded; the home supplies were getting over. Warnings about impending flood came in the mail posts, from the government. As the rain went on, the rivers rose and rose. People had evacuated the danger zones while they had taken shelter in camps, they had lost all their hope of better days. There were rumours of archaic diseases: trench foot, dysentery, cholera etc.

5. Conclusion

While everyone in and around the villages near the High House had perished, the inhabitants of the High House realise that they also will soon have their last days. The High House, though a strong fortress like shelter, wasn't meant to provide the inhabitants shelter till infinity. A time was to come when all the supplies of the house were to get exhausted, its electric supply was to get stalled some time or the other. Till then, the inhabitants had only to wait. They all were conscious of their fast-approaching mortality. Pauly, the youngest member of the house, contemplated about their future, not without truth. The weather being what it was, he realises that he was not far from his death, just like other inmates of the house.

“If I am the last to go, I wonder how long I will stay, after the others are dead. It would not be good to be alone here but worse, I think, to have to make the choice to die without the others there for comfort. I think it will feel very well. I think it will feel very empty. I imagine going round the house for the last time. I imagine shutting the doors. The last of us will not be buried. The last will lie here forever, in the high house, which is our sanctuary, and will be our grave (*The High House* 277).

Thus, we find that towards the end of the novel, Pauly has become mature. He used to love the birds in and around his vicinity but he could face the truth boldly that these birds were likely to perish in such a harsh weather. The inhabitants of the High House had developed resilience and they were aware of their mortality before time.

A climate catastrophe is a soul shattering experience. It has the capability to break a human heart. We find that the inhabitants of the High House, while braving tough situations, grow up to be more courageous and more resilient as they witness a climate catastrophe in its worst form.

Works Cited:

Greengrass, Jessie. *The High House*. Swift Press. London, 2021.

Ospanova, N.K. 'Climate Change and Catastrophe'. *Earth and Environmental Science Research and Reviews*, vol. 7, Issue 01, 2024, pp. 8.

Pierrehumbert, R.T. 'Climate Change: A Catastrophe in Slow Motion.' *Chicago Journal of International Law*, vol. 6, no. 02, 2006, pp. 579.

Richardson, Michael. 'Climate Trauma, or the Affects of the Catastrophe to Come'. *Environmental Humanities*, 2018, pp. 01.